

Utilization of agricultural products for the development of prebiotics in the microencapsulation of synbiotic formulations

Version 1

Description

This Data Management Plan (DMP) describes the handling of data generated within the research project focused on the development and evaluation of synbiotic ingredients and delivery systems based on locally available plant raw materials. The project investigates: the production of resistant starch fractions (RS2 and RS3) from Latvian potato varieties; the extraction and characterisation of xylooligosaccharides (XOS) from barley straw; the in vitro assessment of these prebiotics on the growth and activity of probiotic bacteria (*Bifidobacterium* and *Lactobacillus* spp.); the development of synbiotic microcapsules and evaluation of their physicochemical and microbiological stability.

The DMP outlines procedures for data collection, processing, quality assurance, storage, documentation, sharing, and long-term preservation to ensure data integrity, security, and compliance with ethical requirements and the FAIR principles. Research data will include experimental and process metadata (e.g., raw material characteristics, processing parameters, sample identifiers), analytical outputs (e.g., resistant starch quantification results, HPLC chromatograms and quantified XOS profiles), microbiological fermentation datasets (e.g., CFU counts, growth curves, pH measurements), and microencapsulation characterisation data (e.g., capsule properties, microscopy images, and stability test results).

The project is implemented by the Institute of Agricultural Resources and Economics in collaboration with national and international partners (including the Latvia University of Life Sciences and Technologies and the University of Oviedo), combining expertise in bioprocessing, analytical chemistry, microbiology, and food technology. The DMP specifies that all data will be managed in accordance with applicable legislation and institutional policies. As the project does not involve human participants, personal data processing is

not expected; any incidental personal data (e.g., administrative contact details) will be handled under GDPR and national requirements.

At the end of the project, the datasets underpinning publications and key results will be curated, documented with appropriate metadata and readme files, and deposited in a trusted research data repository that supports persistent identifiers (e.g., DOI) and FAIR-aligned access conditions (e.g., DataverseLV or an equivalent institutional/general repository). Where results have commercialisation or intellectual property potential, access may be provided under justified restrictions (e.g., embargo or controlled access), while still ensuring sufficient transparency for research verification and reuse.

Funder

Latvian Council of Science | | LCS

Grant

Post-doctoral research aid
(Activity 1.1.1.9 "Post-doctoral
Research")

Researchers

Inga Sarenkova (0000-0002-0535-2991)

Organizations

Institute of Agricultural Resources and Economics

1. Main Info

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Researchers:

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Organizations:

Institute of Agricultural Resources and Economics

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2. Funding

Funding organizations: Latvian Council of Science | | LCS

Grants: Post-doctoral research aid (Activity 1.1.1.9 "Post-doctoral Research")

Project:

3. License

License: CC-BY-4.0

Access Rights: Public

Publication Date: 2026-04-01

4. Templates

Descriptions

Production and Characterisation of Resistant Starch RS2 and RS3
from Latvian Potato Cultivars

This dataset contains experimental and analytical data generated to compare three Latvian potato cultivars selected as “starch potato” types due to their relatively higher total starch content compared with other cultivars. Cultivar-level metadata are intentionally limited and include basic identifiers and observable traits, like tuber flesh/skin colour, together with measured starch content. The dataset records processing conditions applied to extract starch and produce resistant starch fractions (RS2 from fresh material and RS3 via retrogradation), with starch extraction performed separately from peeled potato tubers and the peeling by-product consisting of potato skins with a small amount of adhering flesh. The corresponding analytical results include total starch yield and resistant starch content for each fraction and processing condition.

The purpose of the dataset is to provide an evidence base for identifying which of the selected cultivars and which raw material fraction (peeled tuber vs peeling by-product) is most promising for (i) extracting the highest amount of total starch and (ii) achieving the highest resistant starch levels (RS2/RS3). In addition, the dataset is intended to assess whether the potato peeling by-product can serve as a feasible raw material for producing resistant starch-based prebiotics, supporting valorisation of processing residues and more resource-efficient ingredient development.

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

The purpose of the data collection/generation is to compare three Latvian “starch potato” cultivars and two raw material fractions (peeled tuber vs potato peeling by-product consisting of skins with small amounts of adhering flesh) in order to identify the most suitable source material for producing resistant starch (RS2 and RS3) intended for prebiotic applications. The generated data will be used to determine which cultivar allows the highest total starch recovery and the highest resistant starch content, and evaluate whether the peeling by-product can serve as a feasible and valuable raw material for resistant starch-based prebiotic ingredient production. These results directly support the project objective of developing

locally sourced, value-added prebiotic ingredients and selecting the most promising materials for subsequent fermentation and synbiotic formulation work.

Data will be generated through laboratory-scale experiments using potatoes from three selected Latvian starch-type cultivars. Starch will be extracted separately from peeled tubers and from the peeling by-product, followed by production of RS2 (from fresh material) and RS3 (via retrogradation). The dataset will include basic sample descriptors (e.g., cultivar identifier, observable tuber characteristics, measured starch content), processing parameters, and analytical results (e.g., starch yield and resistant starch quantification), recorded and curated by the postdoctoral researcher.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Experimental data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

- TXT
- PDF
- CSV
- TIFF
- JPG

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

1

GB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

No. The dataset will be generated as primary data through new laboratory experiments (starch extraction from peeled tubers and from the peeling by-

product, followed by RS2/RS3 production and quantification). Existing publications and reference information may be used only to inform the methodology, but no external dataset will be re-used as a source of data for this dataset.

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

The data will be useful to researchers and laboratories working on resistant starch, prebiotics and functional food ingredients, and for food and bioprocess technologists developing starch-based ingredients, and for potato breeders and agronomy/food-quality researchers interested in cultivar performance related to starch yield and resistant starch potential, and for stakeholders in the potato processing sector who are interested in valorising peeling by-products as a raw material for value-added ingredients.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

Yes

Dublin Core

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

DataCite Metadata Schema (v4.5)

<https://schema.datacite.org/meta/kernel-4.5/>

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

restricted, no access (access is denied, files will be opened only through contact person to the authors)

Restricted during the embargo period to allow publication, the dataset will be made open after the embargo ends.

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

Yes

Comment:

Yes. An embargo will be applied to allow publication of the results (and, if applicable, assessment of commercialisation potential). The dataset will be made openly available after the first related publication is published or at the end of the project.

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

DataverseLV

DataverseLV was selected as the repository because it is a trusted, institutionally supported platform that ensures long-term preservation and open access to research data in compliance with FAIR principles. It provides persistent identifiers (DOIs) via DataCite, supports rich metadata, and allows for the inclusion of accompanying documentation and code. The platform is aligned with Latvian and European open science policies and ensures data discoverability through international indexing services.

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

The dataset will be provided in CSV format, which can be opened with standard spreadsheet software (e.g., Microsoft Excel, LibreOffice Calc) or any text editor, and in PDF format, which can be accessed with widely available PDF readers (e.g., Adobe Acrobat Reader). No specialized software is required.

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

The CSV format is a non-proprietary, machine-readable format that is widely supported by data analysis, spreadsheet, and statistical software, enabling interoperability and integration with other datasets. The PDF format used for documentation is an open standard (ISO 32000) and can be accessed by a wide range of applications. Both formats facilitate long-term accessibility and reuse without dependence on specific proprietary software.

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

Yes

Dictionary of Research Terminology (terms translated from Latvian into English)

<https://www.rsu.lv/en/petniecibas-terminu-vardnica>

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial 4.0

The dataset will be released under the Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial 4.0 (CC BY-NC 4.0) license to allow free access, sharing, and reuse for non-commercial purposes while ensuring that the original creators are properly credited. This license balances openness with protection against commercial exploitation.

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

The dataset will be deposited in DataverseLV with full metadata, accompanying documentation, and a CC BY-NC 4.0 license. This ensures that third parties can access, understand, and reuse the data for non-commercial purposes even after the conclusion of the project. Long-term preservation guarantees persistent accessibility, and DOI assignment provides a persistent identifier that supports stable referencing over time.

2.4.3 When will the data be made available for re-use?

2029-06-01

2.4.4 How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?

2059-01-01

The dataset is intended to remain reusable indefinitely. By depositing it in DataverseLV, which provides long-term preservation, DOI assignment, and persistent metadata, the data will be accessible and usable for future research and training purposes.

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

2.4.6 Other relevant remarks

Quality assurance will be ensured through the use of standardized and version-controlled laboratory protocols, clear sample identification, and systematic recording of processing parameters. Analytical measurements will include appropriate controls and replicate measurements where needed, and instrument calibration/verification will be documented. Data entry will be checked for consistency (units, ranges, missing values) and, prior to sharing/preservation,

curated into validated tables (CSV) accompanied by a data dictionary and a README file.

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

European Union Recovery and Resilience Facility. Project “Support for implementing Open Science, developing solutions for research data sharing, and participation in EOSC” (2.1.3.1.i.0/2/23/I/CFLA/002).

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

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Data management process are distributed across planning, collection, processing, documentation, storage, and dissemination. Data collection and validation follow established protocols, documentation and metadata are prepared alongside the dataset, and long-term storage and sharing are managed through an institutional repository, ensuring compliance with FAIR principles and open science policies.

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

After the project’s completion, the resources required for long-term data preservation, access, and management — including the repository, its services, and human resources — will be financed by the Higher Education and Science Information Technology Shared Service Centre

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

- Encryption
- Firewall
- Passwords
- Physical access control

Research data will be stored on the institution's secure network drive/server with role-based access control (project members only; least-privilege principle). Regular automated backups will be performed (e.g., daily incremental and periodic full backups), and recovery procedures will be available through institutional IT services. Data transfers with partners (if needed) will use secure, access-controlled channels (institutional cloud/secure file transfer); data will not be shared via unsecured public links. Portable devices used for field/lab work will be password-protected, and sensitive files will be stored on encrypted storage when used outside the institutional network. Version control and file naming conventions will be applied to prevent accidental overwriting, and integrity checks will be performed during curation prior to publication/deposit.

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

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